

Role of metabolic inhibitors on lipase production by a mutant strain *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀

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Abstract : An isolated mutant strain *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ was capable of producing higher amount of lipase (1916.66 μ MFFA/ml/min) in an optimised medium consisting of (% w/v) – glucose, 2.0; urea, 0.7; K₂HPO₄, 0.3; KCl, 0.05; MgSO₄.7H₂O, 0.05; ZnSO₄.7H₂O, 1 μ g/ml; CoCl₂.6H₂O, 3 μ g/ml; mesoinositol, 5 μ g/ml and castor oil, 1.0 at pH 3.5 in 3 days at a temperature of 30 °C in a shake culture method and rotational speed 150 r.p.m. Lipase production was strongly inhibited by metabolic inhibitors, viz. 2-thiouracil mercuric chloride and potamine sulfate. Cellular growth was also retarded. No lipase production and cellular growth were observed at 0 h addition of inhibitors at 10⁻¹ M/ml, 10⁻² M/ml and 10⁻³ M/ml concentrations.

Keywords : *Rhizopus arrhizus*, lipase.

Introduction

Lipases (EC 3.1.13) triacylglycerol acylhydrolases mainly catalyse the hydrolysis of triacylglycerols to glycerol and free fatty acids. The production of microbial lipase was influenced indirectly by the growth of the organism. Proper metabolism was also regulate the secretion of lipase. Production of lipase was also affected by medium ingredients and changes in environmental conditions. The substances inhibitory for the growth of the organism inhibited the production of lipase also.

Very limited reports has been obtained about the metabolic inhibitors for lipase production. Chopra *et al.* used mercuric chloride, silver nitrate, potassium permanganate, iodoacetate and *p*-chloromercuribenzoate as inhibitors for lipase production by *Aspergillus wentii*¹. Papon and Talon reported that tributyrin inhibited both growth and lipase production at a concentration of 0.1% for *Bacillus thermosphacta* and 1.0% for *Lactobacilli*². Anderson *et al.* studied the inhibition of lipase production from *Pseudomonas fluorescence*³ by dihydroacetic acid at pH 5.0. Lipase production was completely inhibited by acetic acid and sodium benzoate.

In our present investigation, an attempt has been made to study the effect of some metabolic inhibitors for lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀.

Materials and methods :

All the chemicals used were bought from Sigma Chemicals and E. Merck, Germany.

Microorganism : An isolated mutant strain *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ maintained on potato-dextrose-agar slants was used⁴.

Inoculum : The inoculum was prepared by washing the spores from one slant, 1 week old with 10 ml sterile normal saline. Fermentation flasks were inoculated with 5% spore suspension containing 8 × 10⁴ spores/ml.

Inhibitor solutions (viz. sodium benzoate, acetic acid, sodium fluoride, sodium azide, malonic acid, 2,4-DNP, 2-thiouracil, mercuric chloride, sodium arsenite and protamine sulfate) were separately sterilized and added individually to the F.M. at concentrations of 10⁻¹, 10⁻² and 10⁻³ M/ml on 0, 24, 36 and 48 h of fermentation. One control set (without any inhibitor supplementation) was used for each set of experiment.

After each set of fermentation, lipolytic activities and dry cellular weight were measured.

Determination of lipolytic activity : Lipolytic activities in the filtrates of fermentation broth was estimated according to the method of Renshaw and San Clemente⁵ based on titration of free acids liberated by lipases from castor oil. One unit of lipase activity was recorded as μ

mole of free fatty acids liberated per ml per minute ($\mu\text{MFFA}/\text{ml}/\text{min}$).

Determination of dry cellular weight : After fermentation, broth was filtered off and the mycelia in filter paper was kept in drier at 80°C for 24 h and then weight of the mycelia was taken after 30 min interval until a constant weight was observed.

Statistical analysis : All values were expressed as mean \pm SEM, where $n = 6$; $*p < 0.05$, $**p < 0.01$. Values were statistically analysed by one way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's post hoc multiple comparison test using 'prism 4.0' software.

Results and discussion

Effect of metabolic inhibitors on lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ :

Figs. 1 to 5 represents the effect of different meta-

bolic inhibitors on lipase production. From Figs. 1–5, it has been observed that lipase production was inhibited by all the metabolic inhibitors used. Cellular growth was also affected in each stage which was related to lipase production. From Figs. 4 and 5, it has been observed that 2-thiouracil, mercuric chloride and protamine sulfate completely inhibited the growth of the organism as well as lipase production when these were added at '0' h or fermentation. After 24 h, there were little growth of the organism and low level of lipase production has been observed which gradually increased with increase in time of addition. Among the other inhibitors tested above (Fig. 3) – malonic acid and 2,4-DNP also remarkably affected the cellular growth as well as decreased the production of lipase.

Fig. 1. Effect of sodium benzoate and acetic acid on lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM; where $n = 6$; $*p < 0.05$. $**p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Fig. 2. Effect of sodium fluoride and sodium azide on lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean \pm SEM; where $n = 6$; $*p < 0.05$. $**p < 0.01$ when compared to control).

Note

Fig. 3. Effect of malonic acid and 2,4-DNP on lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean ± SEM; where n = 6; *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01 when compared to control).

Fig. 4. Effect of thiouracil and mercuric chloride on lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean ± SEM; where n = 6; *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01 when compared to control).

Fig. 5. Effect of protamine sulfate and sodium arsenite on lipase production by *Rhizopus arrhizus* AB₁₀₀ (values were expressed as mean ± SEM; where n = 6; *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01 when compared to control).

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